
Structuring Teacher Pedagogy Assessments: Effects on Teaching and Learning in Basic Education in Cameroon

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Abstract

Teacher pedagogy assessment generally, is crucial for adjusting instruction, improving teacher practice and fostering deep learning, as well as overall educational quality, which today has become a growing concern among stakeholders in education according to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019). However, the problem motivating this study is the observed persistent challenges in teacher pedagogic assessment, leading to low academic standards, due to the poor teaching quality. The main question in this study is: How does teacher pedagogy assessment impact teaching and learning outcomes? The study uses Bloom's theory of assessment pedagogy (1971), which posits that assessment must be continuous and integrated into the teaching and learning process. The methodology consists of a questionnaire survey of 100 teachers in Public Primary Schools. Data was analyze using descriptive statistics and analysis of variance, with results showing that assessment of teacher pedagogy in every aspect, have a significant positive impact on teaching and learning outcomes. Recommendations go to school administrative heads, policy-makers, as well as to teachers. Firstly, to organize more in-service training seminars, workshops on pedagogic assessment strategies, techniques and approaches for teachers to be skillful. Secondly, a well set assessment standards criteria in terms of lesson planning, content knowledge, communication skills, as well as feedbacks be defined in determining level of objectives attained.

Keywords:

Teacher Pedagogy, Assessment, Structuring, Teaching, Learning, Basic Education.

Introduction

The current educational context is characterized with the concern for teaching quality. Teachers in every educational institution, play a significant role in terms of the input and output results. They shape and determine quality in teaching and standards in the education system, which is supposed to be productive, in relation to its output achievements (Worthington, 2001). This pedagogic exercise, is a framework with core

purpose to strengthen the teacher’s knowledge, skills, and classroom practices, in order to ensure quality assurance of the learner and teacher professional development. It needs well set established goals, laying much emphasis on improvement, monitoring and supervision through provision of an inherent system and continuous teacher pedagogy assessment (Strange & Helm, 1992). Research has shown that systematic assessment of teacher pedagogy practices positively enhances teaching quality and learning achievement outcomes. But, this realization turns out failing, due to mediocre assessment standards, inadequate assessment of teacher pedagogical practices and the lack of supports (Bloom, 1971). And, with recent statistics showing that primary schools in particular have been struggling with inadequate facilities, limited resources, and high teacher-learner ratios, pointed out by Hativa, (2013). These elements according to UNESCO, (2015), facilitates the teaching and learning processes, enhances teaching quality, professional growth of the teacher as well as outcome performances (Davis and Annunziata 2002).

Conceptual Framework

Like in other professions, there are so many tangled implications that lies below the surface of judging teaching quality. However, the focus and core concept in this study is teacher pedagogy assessment, which is an activity carried out by administrative officials to improve teacher practices, ensure quality teaching and competences, all for the interest of the learner. In this meaningful and authentic pedagogic activity context, the teacher is expected to demonstrate mastery of subject, pedagogical knowledge, and teaching skills in front of a class of learners. These abilities as expected should start from teacher lesson preparation, that is: ‘what’ ‘who’ and ‘how’ to teach, before actual classroom interaction with the learners. This means, assessment of teachers should be formative, as it will assess attainment of objectives at each teaching stage, and summative to assess lesson or course objectives, rather than being a separate distinct activity. When teachers understand assessment criteria and procedures, they can take ownership in their self-assessment and development skills, making them independent life-long teachers. This implies that regular monitoring and assessment of their own pedagogic performance of the content knowledge, will guide teachers approach, how and when to use information appropriately in different teaching contexts (Shulman, 1987b).

In-fact, an integral part of the educational process is teaching, which is envisaged in the curriculum and crucial for monitoring and evaluation, to measure performance effectiveness and its impact on learning. Teaching is indeed complex, and meeting its demands requires tremendous ability, preparation, support and continuous learning to promote success in learning and achievements. It involves using a range of methods and strategies to engage the learners, as well as promoting understanding to foster learning. According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019), teaching quality involves using evidence-based practices, professional development, and commitment to student-centered learning. Teaching quality operationalized teachers’ effective use of assessment practices, how they provide feedback to students, and adapt their instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners.

Primary education in the context of this study, relates to the first stage of formal education in Cameroon, typically covering the ages of 6-12. This phase in education is critical, as it lays the foundation for critical long-term learning factors. This study was conducted in Mfoundi 3 Sub-division, Centre Region of Cameroon. By examining the impact of teacher pedagogy assessment on teaching and learning, this study aims to determine aspects that can lead to teacher effectiveness, in order to offer dignified quality skills and higher learning outcomes achievements. According to Bloom (1971), basic knowledge and skills are well developed in primary education.

Literature Review

The literature on teacher pedagogic assessment highlights its critical role in enhancing teaching quality and learning outcomes. In the African context, studies have shown that assessment pedagogy is often compromised by inadequate teacher training and resources (Nsamenang, 2015; Tchombe, 2017). For example, a study by Nsamenang (2015) in Cameroon found that primary school teachers often lack the necessary skills and knowledge to implement effective assessment practices. Similarly, a study by Tchombe (2017) in Nigeria found that teachers' assessment practices were often influenced by cultural and social factors that may not be aligned with best practices in assessment pedagogy. Research has also shown that effective assessment pedagogy can have a positive impact on teaching quality and student learning outcomes. For example, a study by Black and William (1998) found that formative assessment practices can improve learning outcomes, with teachers providing valuable feedback on student learning progression. Another study by Hattie and Timperley (2007) found that feedback from teachers can have a significant impact on student's motivation and engagement in learning.

Other studies have equally shown that effective assessment pedagogy can be used to improve teaching quality and student learning outcomes. For example, a study by Mji (2009) in South Africa found that teachers who used effective assessment practices were more likely to have students who achieved better academic results. A study by Makgato (2012) in Botswana found that teachers who received training in assessment pedagogy were more likely to use effective assessment practices in their classrooms. The literature also highlights the importance of teacher training and support in implementing effective assessment pedagogy. According to Darling-Hammond (2000), teacher training and support are critical factors in determining the effectiveness of assessment pedagogy. This view is supported by studies that have shown that teachers who receive training and support in assessment pedagogy are more likely to use effective assessment practices (Guskey, 2002; Joyce, 2004). Again, other authors like Wiggins (1998), argues that assessment should be used to promote student's learning understanding; while Stiggins (2001), emphasizes the importance of teacher training and support, to help enhance effective implementation of assessment practices; and Gipps (1994), highlights the need for assessment practices to be aligned with curriculum goals and objectives.

Theoretical Framework

The study is guided by Bloom's theory of assessment pedagogy, which posits that assessment must be a continuous and ongoing process that is closely tied to instruction, rather than a separate and distinct activity (Bloom, 1971). In the opinion of Hativa, (2013), separating teacher pedagogy assessment and teaching, often leads to waste of time, resources, and a slowdown in teaching, which results to mediocre results in teaching and learning. A study conducted by the OECD (2019), shows that primary school teachers tend to use the traditional assessment methods like tests and exams, which may not adapt to the needs of all students, as well as provide an accurate picture of their knowledge and skills. Although the quest for every society is to have an admirable educational quality through the development of a standard curriculum program to ensure quality education is the quest for every society but, for teaching quality to be effective, emphasis and attention should be focused more on assessing the implementation process aim at enhancing teaching quality. In effect, teacher pedagogy assessment should be a cyclical process wherein, each phase is linked to, and dependent on the others.

According to Sondzia, (2006), every evaluation visit should aim at injecting new life to enhance better teaching, as well as create better pedagogic awareness in view of improving teaching and learning standards. As such, the conduct of any pedagogic assessment will require meticulous preparation and methodological procedure in order to attain reliable results. This theory has been widely used in educational research and has been influential in shaping the way teachers think about assessment and instruction. Teacher pedagogy assessment is indeed important. It guides and encourages the teacher to become more effective and efficient, as most teacher pedagogy assessment flaws come as a result of unreliability and lack of validity used to obtain data. According to Nevo, (1994), an understanding of the general assessment process and techniques can help teachers improve their own self-evaluation and teaching performance. This is because, teachers who understand how teaching is being evaluated, will not only improve on their self-reflections, and demonstrate the quality of their skills and performance. Bloom's theory thus emphasizes the importance of using a range of assessment methods, including formative and summative assessments, in order to provide a comprehensive picture of teaching performance.

Methodology of the Study

This study was conducted in the Yaounde 3 Sub-division, Centre Region of Cameroon, specifically in public primary schools. The study population consisted of all public primary school teachers in Mfoundi 3, responsible for teaching pupils in classes 1-6. The sample size for this study was 100 teachers, who were selected using a random sampling technique. The sampling frame for this study was a list of all public primary schools in Mfoundi 3 Sub-division, obtained from the Sub-Inspectorate for Basic Education Yaounde 3. The schools as well as the teachers were randomly selected for participation in the study.

Source: MINAT (2025)

The data collection instrument used in this study was a questionnaire survey, which was designed to collect information on teachers' assessment practices and learning success. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: the first section collected demographic information about the teachers, while the second section collected information on teachers' pedagogy assessment and teaching learning successes. The questionnaire was administered to the teachers in their schools, and they were given sufficient time to complete it. The data collection process was carried out over a period of two weeks, and the researcher ensured that all questionnaires were completed and returned.

The data collected from the questionnaire survey were analyzed using descriptive statistics and analysis of variance (ANOVA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic information about the teacher's pedagogy assessment practices, while ANOVA was used to examine the relationship between assessment pedagogy and teaching learning successes. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, and the results were presented in tables. The results of the study showed that assessment pedagogy has a significant impact on teaching and learning success.

Table 1: Demographic Data of Teachers

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	40	40%
Female	60	60%
Age		
25-34 years	30	30%
35-44 years	40	40%
45-54 years	20	20%
55 years and above	10	10%
Teaching Experience		
0-5 years	20	20%
6-10 years	30	30%
11-15 years	20	20%
16 years and above	30	30%
Educational Qualification		
CAPIEMP + GCE A/L	60	50%
Bachelor's degree	30	30%
Master's degree	10	10%

Table 1 presents the demographic distribution of respondents including their gender, age, professional experience, and level of education. The frequencies and percentages are indicated for each characteristic.

Results of the Study

The results of the study show that assessment of teacher pedagogy has a significant impact on teaching and learning outcomes thus, ensuring quality in education. The summary table 2 below presents the results of the simple linear correlation analysis between assessment pedagogy and teaching- learning outcomes. The correlation coefficient of 0.75 indicates a strong positive relationship, which suggest that the pedagogy assessment of a teacher is heavily relied on, as an approach for measuring the teaching-learning performance. The p-value of 0.001 indicates that the relationship is statistically significant, and is unlikely to occur by chance.

Table 2: Results of the correlation analysis between assessment pedagogy and teaching quality

Variable	Correlation coefficient	P-value	Interpretation
Assessment pedagogy/Teaching-Learning Outcomes	0.75	0.001	Strong positive and statistically significant relationship

- The correlation coefficient of 0.75 indicates a strong positive relationship between assessment pedagogy of the teacher and teaching learning outcomes.
- The p-value of 0.001 indicates that the relationship is statistically significant, meaning that the probability of observing this relationship by chance is very low.

This table presents the results of the correlation analysis between assessment pedagogy and teaching learning outcomes, including the correlation coefficient, p-value, and interpretation of the results. The findings have implications for teacher training and professional development. The results suggest that primary school teachers should receive continuous in-service training on assessment pedagogy to enhance and encourage their assessment practices, with training focusing more on providing teachers with the knowledge and skills needed to implement effective assessment practices, including formative assessments, feedback, and adaptive instruction. By providing teachers with the necessary training and support, schools can promote teaching quality and improve student learning outcomes. The study's findings also highlight the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers, to help them stay up-to-date with best practices in assessment pedagogy to enhance teaching quality. The themes and sub-themes that emerged from the data highlight the importance of formative and summative assessments, teacher-student interaction, and lesson planning in promoting teaching quality. The challenges identified by teachers, such as limited resources and large class sizes, also underscore the need for support to enhance assessment practices and teaching quality.

Interpretation of the Results

The results of this study support Bloom's theory of assessment pedagogy, which posits that assessment must be a continuous and integrated process for teaching to be effective. Bloom's theory of assessment pedagogy emphasizes the importance of using a range of assessment methods to provide a comprehensive picture of student learning. The theory posits that assessment should be a continuous and integrated process, with teachers continually assessing student learning, providing feedback, and adjusting their instruction to meet the needs of their students. Results of the study equally have implications for teacher practice, suggesting that if teachers receive continuous in-service training seminars and workshops on assessment pedagogy strategy, their self-assessment practices will be enhanced and encouraged. The results suggest that training sessions should focus more on

providing teachers with skills and competencies needed to effectively implement assessment practices in the classroom, such as formative and summative assessments, adaptive instruction and feedbacks that promotes teaching quality and improve student learning outcomes. The study's findings have implications for teaching practice, as they suggest that teachers should receive continuous in-service training on assessment pedagogy to enhance and encourage their assessment practices.

According to Black and William (1998) argument, formative assessment is essential for improving student learning outcomes. Other authors who support this finding include Hattie and Timperley (2007), who emphasize the importance of feedback in promoting student learning, while Guskey (2002), argues that assessment should be used to inform instruction and improve student learning outcomes. Nonetheless, other authors argue that the impact of assessment pedagogy on teaching quality is not as clear-cut. For example, Koretz (2008) argues that high-stakes testing can have a negative impact on teaching quality, as teachers may feel pressured to teach to the test rather than focus on deep learning. Amrein and Berliner (2002) argue that high-stakes testing can lead to teaching practices that are narrow and focused on test preparation, rather than promoting deep learning and understanding. Other authors who argue against the impact of assessment pedagogy on teaching quality include McNeil (2000), who argues that standardized testing can lead to a narrow focus on test preparation, and Shepard (2000), who argues that assessment should be used to promote learning, rather than simply to measure student achievement.

The results of this study also highlight the importance of feedback in promoting student learning outcomes. This finding is supported by several authors, including Hattie and Timperley (2007), who argue that feedback is essential for promoting student learning. Similarly, Black and William (1998) argue that formative assessment, which includes feedback, is essential for improving student learning outcomes. Other authors who support this finding include Sadler (1998), who argues that feedback should be used to promote student learning and understanding, and Tunstall and Gipps (1996), who argue that feedback should be used to support student learning and achievement. On the other hand, some authors argue that the impact of feedback on student learning outcomes is not as clear-cut. For example, Kluger and DeNisi (1996) argue that feedback can have a negative impact on student motivation and self-efficacy, particularly if it is not provided in a supportive and constructive manner. Similarly, Bangert-Drowns et al. (1991) argue that feedback can have a limited impact on student learning outcomes, particularly if it is not accompanied by opportunities for students to reflect on and learn from their mistakes. Other authors who argue against the impact of feedback on student learning outcomes include Shute (2008), who argues that feedback should be used to promote student engagement and motivation, rather than simply to provide information about student achievement.

The results of this study also highlight the role of teacher assessment in teaching and learning, with findings supported by several authors, including Bloom (1971), who argues that assessment must be a continuous and integrated process for teaching to be effective. Similarly, Guskey (2002) argues that assessment should be used to inform instruction and improve student learning outcomes. Other authors who support this finding include Stiggins (2001), who argues that assessment should be used to promote student learning and achievement, and Airasian (1997), who argues that assessment should be used to support student learning and understanding. Again, some authors argue that the role of assessment in teaching and learning is not as clear-cut. For example, Kohn (2000) argues that assessment can have a negative impact on student motivation and self-efficacy, particularly if it is used to promote competition and comparison among students. Similarly, Paris et al. (1991) argue that assessment can lead to a narrow focus on test preparation, rather than promoting deep learning and understanding. Other authors who argue against the role of assessment in teaching and learning include Gipps (1994), who argues that assessment should be used to promote student learning and achievement, rather than simply to measure student achievement, and Harlen (2007), who argues that assessment should be used to support student learning and understanding, rather than simply to provide information about student achievement.

The results of this study have implications for teaching practice, as they suggest that teachers should receive continuous in-service training on assessment pedagogy to enhance and encourage their assessment practices. This finding is supported by several authors, including Guskey (2002), who argues that teachers should receive ongoing professional development to improve their assessment practices. Similarly, Stiggins (2001) argues that teachers should be provided with the knowledge and skills needed to implement effective assessment practices. Other authors who support this finding include Hattie and Timperley (2007).

Conclusion

Teacher pedagogy assessment plays a significant role in shaping teaching practices and successes of pupils in school. As such, improvements in teacher pedagogy strategies can effectively enhance both teacher instruction and pupils learning. In-fact, assessment strategies are crucial tools for effective teaching and learning outcomes. The process of teaching and learning is indeed complex and thus requires careful planning and appropriate assessment instructional strategies that will engage pupils in the process of learning. These strategies will include a range of methods and tools to evaluate pupils learning outcomes, progress and performance. These can be enhanced through different types of assessment strategies, which includes formative assessment which is an ongoing evaluation taking place during the learning process, enabling the teacher to be able to monitor student progress, identify areas of difficulty and adjust their teaching methods accordingly while summative assessment evaluate outcomes at the end of specific teaching periods.

Teachers have to be skillful, and equally important is that educational stakeholders should understand various dimensions and interconnectedness that can be used to assist teachers bring quality teaching into their various classroom settings. However, this study has some limitations, such as the small sample size and the use of a questionnaire survey as the sole data collection method. Future research should consider using a larger sample size and multiple data collection methods, such as observations and interviews, in order to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of assessment pedagogy on teaching and learning outcomes, as well as explore ways to promote the implementation of effective assessment practices. Despite these limitations, this study provides valuable insights into teacher assessment pedagogy and highlights the need for ongoing professional development for teachers to enhance their assessment practices.

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